
Research

The Development of an Intelligent System for Treating Brain Hyperthermia

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Abstract: The apparatus is engineered for treating brain hyperthermia through convective heat transfer, facilitating swift intervention for patients suffering from this condition. The primary goal of the project is to offer emergency relief to prevent severe outcomes, including permanent disability or death, due to the patient's inability to regulate body temperature effectively. The system employs a non-contact forced convection method, uniformly distributing cooling air across the patient's body. Adapted from previous work, the apparatus includes a heat exchanger and mechanical components with four independent sections of compressed air pipes. These pipes feature orifice openings positioned around a specially designed mannequin that simulates the human body. This mannequin is constructed from a polyester core wrapped with tightly coiled soft PVC pipe, and covered with polyethylene sheets to mimic the skin's dermis and epidermis layers. The mannequin is equipped with four thermal patches (head, upper abdomen, lower abdomen, and leg) and can achieve a temperature of 44°C when hot water circulates through it at a flow rate of 7 liters per minute. Cooling air is managed by a control valve that adjusts based on deviations from the normal body temperature of 37°C. The air is directed to specific regions of the mannequin, with a thermocouple providing data to a fuzzy controller, which in turn regulates the airflow to maintain the desired temperature.

Keywords: Brain hyperthermia, Fuzzy logic control, IoT integration, Thermocouple sensors, Convective heat transfer.

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Accepted: 21 October, 2024; **Published:** 22 October, 2024

How to cite this article: Jibon Miah, Md Khalid Saifullah, Saikat Gharami, Md Mofezur Rahaman Milon (2024). The Development of an Intelligent System for Treating Brain Hyperthermia. *North American Academic Research*, 7(10), 48-59. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13989144>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Elevated brain temperature, commonly known as fever or hyperthermia, is a serious medical condition caused by factors such as infections, traumatic brain injuries, and strokes. This condition can result in severe neurological damage

and, if left untreated, can be fatal. Traditional treatments for hyperthermia often involve invasive procedures or medications that can be harmful. Therefore, there is a pressing need for new, non-invasive methods to effectively manage brain hyperthermia [1].

This project aims to develop and implement an intelligent control system using fuzzy logic technology to address brain hyperthermia. The system is designed to cool the patient's elevated brain temperature by directing air over various parts of the body. To test and demonstrate the system's functionality, a mannequin mimicking human thermal and blood flow responses is used. This dummy serves as a stand-in for a human patient during testing [2][3].

The fuzzy logic controller, a type of machine learning technique, is chosen for its ability to manage the uncertainties and non-linearities associated with temperature control. The controller processes temperature inputs from sensors and adjusts the airflow accordingly. It categorizes temperature into five levels—deficient, low, medium, high, very high, and extremely high—and adjusts the valve opening to regulate the cooling air based on these categories [4][5]. The fuzzy logic controller, which acts as the system's brain, receives temperature data from MAX6675 sensors placed on the mannequin. These sensors, known for their precision and reliability in high-temperature environments, provide real-time temperature readings. The data is processed by an ESP32 microcontroller, which uses the fuzzy logic algorithm to determine the appropriate flow rate and adjust the stepper motor, thereby controlling the gate valve and the airflow rate [6][7].

The cooling air is delivered through helical pipes wrapped around the mannequin, with strategically placed orifices ensuring even distribution. The Blynk platform is used for real-time monitoring and visualization of temperature data, allowing healthcare providers to oversee the cooling process remotely and ensure it remains within safe limits [9][10].

The accuracy of temperature measurement is critical to the system's effectiveness. MAX6675 thermocouple sensors are calibrated against a standard mercury thermometer to ensure their precision. Temperature data is collected every second and fed into the fuzzy logic controller for immediate and accurate adjustments [8].

By integrating IoT technology, the system offers remote monitoring capabilities via the Blynk platform, enabling continuous oversight of the patient's condition and facilitating prompt intervention if necessary [11][12][13].

This project marks a significant advancement in treating brain hyperthermia by combining fuzzy logic control with IoT technology to create a non-invasive, efficient, and user-friendly solution. Successful implementation could lead to further advancements in automated medical treatment systems, enhancing patient outcomes and reducing reliance on traditional invasive methods [14][15].

Research Methodology

The approach taken in this study involves the development and implementation of an intelligent controller for the treatment of brain hyperthermia. The methodology revolves around a controlled spray cooling mechanism, leveraging convective heat transfer principles to achieve the desired temperature reduction. The overall workflow involves monitoring the temperature rise, actuating a control valve, and spraying cool air to normalize the temperature of the mannequin, which simulates human thermal characteristics.

Optimization of Mannequin Design

Mannequin Assembly

The design of the mannequin was optimized to replicate the thermal characteristics of a brain hyperthermia patient. The mannequin, segmented into patches for the head, chest, abdomen, and legs, was constructed with a polyster core tightly wound with PVC pipes. These patches were connected to the main fluid supply network, which included a pump and a reservoir to ensure a steady and controlled flow of the cooling medium.

Repair and Testing

Initial tests highlighted issues such as leakages and blockages in the inlet and outlet networks. To address these, the pipes were replaced with PPR-water supply pipes known for their low thermal conductivity and durability. This ensured a smooth flow of water. Blockages caused by water sensors were cleared to ensure an uninterrupted flow. Trapped air within the system was vented using pressurized water supplied by a hydraulic bench, ensuring consistent fluid flow.

Figure 1:

Uniform fluid distribution was achieved by adjusting gate valves attached to each mannequin patch. Flow sensors were used to maintain a consistent flow rate of 1.1L/min per patch, corresponding to an overall flow rate of 7L/min, which simulates the human blood perfusion rate.

Figure 2:**Temperature Sensor Network**

Accurate temperature measurement is crucial for the effective functioning of the system. K-type thermocouples, interfaced with an ESP32 microcontroller, were attached to each patch of the mannequin to monitor temperature changes in real-time. The core temperature was monitored to reach 44°C, replicating hyperthermia conditions. Feedback from these thermocouples was used to dynamically adjust the control valve, ensuring precise temperature regulation.

Heat Exchanger Coils

The heat exchanger coils, a critical component for cooling, were designed and optimized for performance. PVC pipes were selected for their elliptical shape and appropriate dimensions, and orifices were designed to ensure effective cooling. Simulation studies were conducted to validate the performance of the heat exchanger, and adjustments were made to optimize the orifice geometries for uniform cooling [15][16].

Electronic Components Integration

Several electronic components were integrated into the system to enhance functionality. The K-type thermocouples with MAX6675 interfaces provided precise temperature measurements. The ESP32 microcontroller handled data processing and Wi-Fi connectivity, while an LCD display facilitated real-time data visualization. A stepper motor and driver were used for the control valve actuation, enabling precise regulation of airflow.

Flow Control Valve Design

The flow control valve, essential for regulating airflow, was meticulously designed and integrated. Components included a needle valve, a shaft coupler, a stepper motor, and a driver. The stepper motor's angular motion was converted to linear displacement to adjust the valve precisely. The control system ensured that the valve opened and closed in response to temperature feedback, maintaining optimal cooling.

The mathematical relationship governing the control valve's operation can be expressed as:

$$\Delta T = \frac{T_{\text{desired}} - T_{\text{measured}}}{T_{\text{range}}}$$

Airflow Adjustment = Fuzzy Logic Controller (ΔT)

Control System Design

A closed-loop control system was developed to regulate the mannequin's temperature effectively. This system consisted of an actuator (control valve), a fuzzy logic-based controller, and a feedback loop. Cool air was supplied through heat exchanger coils, and the control valve adjusted based on temperature feedback from the thermocouples. The fuzzy logic controller utilized temperature input and airflow output to maintain the desired temperature, with control rules and membership functions implemented using MATLAB.

IoT Integration

To enhance system functionality, IoT technology was integrated. The Blynk platform was used for remote monitoring, with the ESP32 microcontroller facilitating Wi-Fi connectivity and real-time data transmission. Gauge widgets were set up for temperature display, and secure communication protocols ensured reliable remote monitoring and control.

Modeling and Simulation

Comprehensive modeling and simulation were conducted to validate system performance. CAD models were developed, and simulations of the heat exchanger's performance were carried out. The stepper motor's motion was mathematically modeled to ensure precise valve actuation, thereby validating the control system's effectiveness.

By adhering to this detailed methodology, the project aims to provide a reliable, non-invasive solution for brain hyperthermia treatment, utilizing advanced control systems and IoT integration to improve patient outcomes [26][27].

Temperature Sensor Network

Sensor Setup

K-type thermocouples were attached to various patches on the mannequin to ensure accurate temperature measurement. These thermocouples were connected to an ESP32 microcontroller, which handled data processing and displayed the results on an LCD. This setup facilitated real-time monitoring and immediate adjustments based on temperature changes.

Thermal Characteristics

The system was designed to maintain a uniform thermal gradient within the mannequin. The core temperature was monitored and controlled to reach 44°C. Feedback from the thermocouples was used to adjust the control valve dynamically, ensuring the mannequin accurately replicated the thermal conditions of a brain hyperthermia patient [24][25].

Heat Exchanger Coils

Design and Material Selection

PVC pipes were selected for constructing the heat exchanger coils due to their suitable properties. The pipes were designed with elliptical shapes and precise dimensions to facilitate effective cooling. Orifices were carefully designed and dimensioned to ensure the efficient distribution of cool air across the mannequin's surface [22][23].

Optimization

Simulation studies were conducted to validate the performance of the heat exchanger. The efficiency of heat transfer was assessed through computational models. Necessary adjustments were made to the orifice geometries to optimize cooling performance. This process ensured that the cooling mechanism was effective and maintained the desired thermal conditions within the mannequin.

5. Electronic Components Integration

Components Used

The integration of electronic components was critical to the system's functionality. The components included K-type thermocouples with MAX6675 interfaces for precise temperature sensing, an ESP32 microcontroller for data processing and Wi-Fi connectivity, an LCD display for real-time data visualization, and a stepper motor with a driver for accurate valve control. These components were selected for their reliability and compatibility with the overall control system.

Component Functions

Each component played a vital role in ensuring the system's effectiveness:

Temperature Sensing: The K-type thermocouples provided accurate temperature readings. The MAX6675 interface converted these readings into a digital format suitable for processing [20][21].

Data Processing: The ESP32 microcontroller processed the temperature data and managed the system's operations, including sending data for remote monitoring via Wi-Fi.

Display: The LCD, connected via an I2C module, displayed real-time temperature data, allowing for immediate visual monitoring.

Control Mechanisms: The stepper motor and driver regulated the valve's position, controlling the airflow to maintain the desired temperature. The stepper motor's angular displacement θ is calculated as:

$$\theta = \frac{N_{\text{stega}} \times 360^\circ}{N_{\text{total steps}}}$$

6. Flow Control Valve Design

Components

The flow control valve, essential for precise airflow regulation, comprised a needle valve, a shaft coupler, a stepper motor, and a driver. These components were selected for their precision and compatibility with the system's requirements.

Mechanism

The stepper motor was employed to adjust the valve, converting its angular motion into linear displacement. This precise control ensured that the airflow could be finely tuned in response to temperature changes, maintaining optimal cooling. The relationship between the stepper motor steps and the valve opening is given by:

7. Control System Design

Closed-loop System

A closed-loop control system was developed to effectively regulate the mannequin's temperature. This system included an actuator (the control valve), a fuzzy logic-based controller, and a feedback loop. Cool air was supplied through heat exchanger coils, with the control valve adjusting based on feedback from the thermocouples.

Fuzzy Logic Controller

The fuzzy logic controller was central to the system, using temperature inputs from the thermocouples to regulate the airflow rate and maintain the desired temperature. The control rules and membership functions were implemented using MATLAB. The fuzzy logic control system can be described by the following steps:

Input: Temperature data from the thermocouples.

Rule Evaluation: The fuzzy logic controller evaluates the input data against predefined rules to determine the necessary valve adjustments.

Output: The controller adjusts the airflow rate to maintain the desired temperature.

The mathematical expression for the control logic is:

$$\Delta T = T_{\text{measured}} - T_{\text{desired}}$$

where ΔT is the temperature difference, T_{measured} is the temperature recorded by the thermocouples, and T_{desired} is the target temperature of 37°C .

The fuzzy logic inference process involves:

IF T_{measured} IS HIGH THEN Valve Opening IS WIDE

The valve adjustment (Valve Opening) is calculated based on the fuzzy logic function:

$$\text{Valve Opening} = f(T_{\text{measured}}, \text{Rules})$$

where f maps the temperature input to the valve opening based on the predefined rules.

This comprehensive methodology ensures a reliable, non-invasive solution for treating brain hyperthermia, utilizing advanced control systems and IoT integration to improve patient outcomes.

8. IoT Integration

The integration of IoT technology was essential for enhancing the functionality and usability of the brain hyperthermia treatment system. The Blynk platform was utilized for remote monitoring, allowing real-time data transmission and control via Wi-Fi connectivity. This setup enabled healthcare providers to monitor the system's performance and patient temperature remotely, ensuring timely and accurate interventions [20][21].

The system design involved the use of an ESP32 microcontroller to handle data processing and Wi-Fi connectivity. The Blynk platform provided a user-friendly interface for real-time data visualization. The implementation steps included setting up gauge widgets on the Blynk dashboard to display temperature readings from the mannequin. These widgets were configured to receive data from the ESP32, ensuring accurate and timely updates.

To ensure secure and efficient remote monitoring, several measures were implemented. The communication between the ESP32 and the Blynk platform was secured using encryption protocols. Additionally, access controls and authentication mechanisms were established to protect the data and control functions from unauthorized access [17][18][19].

The real-time data transmission was governed by the following equation:

$$R(t) = f(T_{\text{measured}}, t)$$

where $R(t)$ is the real-time data transmitted to the Blynk platform, T_{measured} is the temperature measured by the thermocouples, and t is the time parameter.

9. Modeling and Simulation

To ensure the system's performance and reliability, extensive modeling and simulation were conducted for both the heat exchanger and the control valve.

For the heat exchanger, CAD modeling was employed to design the coils and simulate their performance. The simulation analyzed the heat transfer efficiency and airflow dynamics, ensuring that the design met the required cooling performance. The heat transfer rate Q in the heat exchanger was modeled using the equation:

$$Q = \dot{m}c_p\Delta T$$

where Q is the heat transfer rate, $\dot{m}$ is the mass flow rate of the cooling air, c_p is the specific heat capacity of air, and ΔT is the temperature difference between the inlet and outlet air.

The control valve modeling involved converting the stepper motor's angular motion into precise valve actuation. This conversion was critical for regulating the airflow based on the temperature feedback. The stepper motor's motion was mathematically modeled to ensure accurate response and control. The relationship between the stepper motor steps and the valve displacement was given by:

$$x = r\theta$$

where x is the linear displacement of the valve, r is the radius of the valve stem, and θ is the angular displacement of the stepper motor.

The mathematical modeling of the control valve's response included determining the number of steps required for the stepper motor to achieve the desired valve opening. This was calculated using the equation:

$$N_{\text{steps}} = \frac{x \times N_{\text{total steps}}}{360^\circ}$$

where N_{steps} is the number of steps required, x is the desired linear displacement, and $N_{\text{total steps}}$ is the total number of steps for a full rotation of the stepper motor.

By conducting these detailed simulations and modeling, the system's design was validated, ensuring that the heat exchanger and control valve performed as expected under various operating conditions. This comprehensive approach guaranteed the effectiveness and reliability of the brain hyperthermia treatment system.

Modeling and Simulation

Simulation Of Heat Exchanger:

A heat exchanger coil designed for a chest patch with dimensions of $h = 18$ inches and $l = 33$ inches is shown in Figure 4.2. At an ambient temperature of 25 degrees, the simulation results show that there is a negligible temperature drop from the inlet to the outlet of the hot water flowing through the pipe.

Motion Conversion:

We have modified the manually operated gate valve into an electrical control valve by coupling it with a stepper motor. The output motion of the motor is in angular form. We require translation motion to open and close the needle valve.

The stepper motor takes 200 steps to complete one full rotation (360 degrees). The linear displacement of the control valve can be calculated as

$$S = r \cdot \theta$$

Where r is the radius of the valve that is ¼ inch. to fully open the valve motor needs to rotate 5.65π

That means the lever with the spindle of the motor rotates linearly =11.424mm.

4.3 Modelling Of Control Valve Coupling With Actuator:

We design the control valve using a stepper motor and integrate the needle valve then we connect the inlet to the compressor output side which gives us a 7bar pressure supply then we use an airflow measuring device tachometer to measure the response of our control valve we take multiple values at different steps and then plot the response that shows a nonlinear behavior we use curve fitting tool to model an exponential equational of our response. We also use polynomial equations but they give a close response at a 7-degree polynomial to avoid difficulty we use an exponential equation because it gives a very close response to the actual one.

Results and Discussion

5.1 Results:

The previous studies tell us we heat the mannequin at 44 degrees Celsius and then leave it to decrease the temperature to 37 degrees takes approx. 300 minutes when the ambient temperature is 20.5 degrees Celsius, as shown in Figure 4.

But when we heat the mannequin at 44 degrees with the therapy process to decrease the temperature to 37 degrees Celsius it takes approximately 138 minutes at 30 degrees ambient temperature. The below shows the average temperature of all patches with the time constant=58 minutes. which shows a very effective method to decrease the temperature of the mannequin by almost 50 percent time as compared to without therapy.

Conclusion

The focus of our project is the development of an intelligent controller that manages a control valve to ensure precise airflow, effectively normalizing the temperature of the body. We found this process to be highly efficient overall. The implementation of fuzzy logic improved performance, though we encountered challenges with controlling the full scope of the project. One significant issue was air leakage, which, combined with difficulties maintaining a stable pressure of 7 bar (as pressure decreased with the opening of the wall), complicated our efforts. Despite these challenges, we were able to maintain accurate velocity measurements for each patch, as outlined in our documentation.

In our experiments, reducing the temperature to a normal state took approximately 140 minutes, with a time constant of about 58 minutes. However, inadequate insulation of the outlet pipe, which was not covered with insulating materials such as polyester, led to heat loss and extended the time required. Despite this, the results were still significantly better than without the therapy. We anticipate that time efficiency will improve when the ambient temperature is lowered to 25 degrees Celsius.

Monitoring temperature remotely through mobile devices or laptops is feasible, but due to the continuous operation of the compressor, someone must be present to oversee the process and shut it down in case of any alarming situations.

The mannequin designed for our project simulates the human body's response to hyperthermia, demonstrating heat transfer properties accurately. The mannequin replicates human skin layers—inner tissues, epidermis, dermis, and subcutaneous layers—using polyester for the core, tightly coiled with soft PVC pipes, and covered with polyethylene sheets to represent dermal and epidermal layers. This setup forms a three-node thermal model based on human physiology. The mannequin features four patches (head, upper abdomen, lower abdomen, and leg) and achieves a temperature of 44 degrees Celsius when hot water flows through it at a rate of 7 liters per minute.

While conventional cooling methods for brain hyperthermia can be effective, they are often invasive and may not provide the precise control needed for optimal brain temperature regulation. Our intelligent control system, enhanced with fuzzy logic and IoT integration, offers a safer, more efficient, and automated solution, enabling medical staff to monitor and manage temperatures remotely and effectively.

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Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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